

HYPERKERATOSIS AND EARLY FOOT DEFORMITIES IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20067960>

Abstract. The application of the proposed treatment and diagnostic algorithm allowed us to develop a consistent decision-making system based on a quantitative assessment of the degree of local overload and early signs of bone support at the site. This made it possible to use surgical interventions strictly in situations where they are pathogenetically justified.

Keywords: diabetes mellitus, hyperkeratosis, foot deformity

Background. Issues related to the early detection and treatment of hyperkeratosis and overload foot deformities in diabetes mellitus have repeatedly been the subject of research in both clinical endocrinology and orthopedic surgery in recent years. Despite the diversity of approaches, a significant portion of the work reflects primarily attempts to control the consequences of pathological stress, rather than its root cause (1,3,5). At the surgical level, the level of study also remains insufficient (2,4). Surgical solutions have evolved independently of diagnostic approaches, creating a gap between identified disorders and the methods for their correction. Thus, the level of study of this problem is characterized by fragmented approaches, a lack of integrative diagnostic criteria, and insufficient development of minor bone-unloading surgeries as a method of early surgical correction. This confirms the need for a comprehensive study aimed at constructing a quantitative model of overload and creating optimized surgical tactics.

Objective of the study: To develop and comparatively evaluate surgical treatment methods for hyperkeratosis and early foot deformities in patients with diabetes mellitus.

Materials and Methods. The first subgroup included 38 patients (52.8%) with hyperkeratosis without signs of NPP and probability to bone. The inclusion criteria were the absence of soft tissue defects, the absence of significant inflammation, and the absence of subepithelial cavities according to ultrasound data. The second subgroup included 34 patients (47.2%) with PUF confirmed by a combination of clinical features (presence of a defect, maceration, infiltration), a positive probing test, local hyperthermia, and signs of overload involvement of bone structures.

Results and discussion. The results of the multivariate logistic analysis allowed us to determine the quantitative contribution of each parameter to the need for local bone-unloading correction and use these data to develop a comprehensive assessment scale for local overload and bone support of the lesion (COLP). The scale is organized into three sections, reflecting clinical manifestations, baropodometric characteristics of foot support, and radiographic signs of early remodeling of bone structure and configuration.

Each block includes four levels of symptom severity, assigned a score from 0 to 3. This approach ensures a sequential transition from minimal to severe changes, covering the full spectrum of conditions identified in the control group. The first block captures the clinical features of the lesion and begins with mild hyperkeratosis, which is assigned a score of 0, representing a condition without signs of structural instability. Increasing hyperkeratosis severity, the development of discomfort, and episodes of maceration correspond to a score of 1. The most important category within the clinical block is the combination of recurrent hyperkeratosis and an epithelialized subepithelial cavity, reflecting the presence of a latent preulcer; this condition is assigned a score of 2.

The highest severity (3 points) corresponds to a formed ulcer with a localized purulent process in the absence of systemic manifestations. The depth of the defect according to the Wagner classification is recorded separately and is not included in the scoring. This gradation allows for the consideration of three key stages of damage (hyperkeratosis, preulcer, and ulcer), each with its own prognostic value.

The second block reflects the baropodometric signs of pathological support. A score of 0 points is assigned for normal load distribution. A moderate increase in pressure compensated by orthopedic devices is assigned 1 point. A persistent localized peak, persisting during repeated examinations, corresponds to 2 points, indicating stable biomechanical overload. The most pronounced impairment, in the form of a persistent peak in pressure, accompanied by a shift in the center of support toward the pathological zone, is assigned 3 points. This sequence replicates the gradient of the contribution of overload factors revealed by statistical analysis and ensures an accurate quantitative reflection of biomechanical disturbances.

The third block describes the radiographic signs of early bone support of the lesion and begins with 0 points for the absence of changes in the bone structures beneath the lesion. Minimal subchondral changes are recorded as 1 point. A score of 2 points corresponds to a localized bony prominence, erosions,

and initial signs of osteolysis, reflecting the formation of a primary support zone beneath the soft tissue lesion. The maximum severity of the disorder is assessed at 3 points and includes signs of localized osteoarthropathy, subchondral remodeling, and the presence of small sequestrars that do not require extensive resection. This structure allows for the consideration of both early and advanced signs of skeletal overload, which are key factors in determining the surgical approach.

Assigning a specific score to each characteristic provides a summary assessment of the lesion's condition, enabling the scale to be integrated into a digital environment. The scoring system was adapted to a machine learning module, in which the values of each level were included in the model as independent predictors. The algorithm analyzed combinations of characteristics in three blocks and generated a probabilistic assessment of the severity of the pathological support. In the absence of baropodometry or radiographic data, it used clinical and biomechanical patterns established during training. This enabled partial substitution of missing data and significantly reduced the diagnostic burden during initial consultations.

The developed scale served as the basis for subsequent evaluation of its diagnostic effectiveness and comparison with traditional examination methods, which will allow us to determine its value as a tool for selecting surgical treatment tactics and move on to an analysis comparing various diagnostic methods. The development of the "KOLP" scale for a comprehensive assessment of localized overload and bone support in a lesion allowed us to quantitatively characterize the severity of pathological support and generate a numerical indicator reflecting a combination of clinical changes, biomechanical abnormalities, and early bone remodeling. The total score on the "KOLP" scale has proven to be a convenient tool for classifying patients into three groups, differing in the risk of lesion progression and the likelihood of requiring localized bone-unloading correction. This classification allows us to move from a fragmented assessment of a lesion to a decision-making structure, where each score range defines its own LDA trajectory.

The transition to LDA for surgical strategy selection requires combining the obtained score with a sequence of clinical decisions, forming an action tree in which each zone defines its own branch, and the dynamics of the lesion's condition determines the possibility of escalation or de-escalation.

The development of the LDA for surgical strategy selection allowed us to identify two typical surgical interventions aimed at eliminating bone support in

the pathological zone and reducing localized overload. These procedures do not duplicate standard exostectomies and minor resections, but are modified versions based on baropodometry data and early structural changes in the affected area. This approach allows for interventions to be performed in accordance with the actual biomechanics of the patient's foot, improving the accuracy of correction and reducing the likelihood of hyperkeratosis recurrence or the development of a new risk zone.

The use of the proposed LDA has enabled the development of a consistent decision-making system based on a quantitative assessment of the degree of local overload and early signs of bony support in the lesion, making it possible to use surgical interventions strictly in situations where they are pathogenetically justified. This strategy allows for controlled escalation and de-escalation depending on the dynamics of the foot's condition, and the implementation of modified minor surgeries allows for the elimination of structural abnormalities at key stages of progression. The completeness of the LDA and its connection with objective diagnostic methods create the conditions for testing its clinical applicability.

Conclusions:

1. The development of the LDA for surgical strategy selection has enabled the identification of two typical surgical interventions aimed at eliminating bony support in the pathological zone and reducing local overload. These interventions do not duplicate standard exostectomies and minor resections, but rather represent modifications based on baropodometry data and consideration of early structural changes in the lesion area.

2. The use of the proposed LDA allowed us to develop a consistent decision-making system based on a quantitative assessment of the degree of local overload and early signs of bone support of the lesion, making it possible to use surgical interventions strictly in situations where they are pathogenetically justified.

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